

Ecological Compassion and Anthropocentric Obligation: A Comparative Study of Western and Eastern Traditional Philosophies

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Received: Nov 16 , 2025

Accepted: Dec 13, 2025

Published: Dec 15, 2025

Abstract:

These two eastern and western traditions develop deep respect and reverence for all forms life by considering the environment as sacred filled with divinity. Both Western and Eastern philosophies present metaphysical worldview as well as ecological concern. Universe and God are identical. Divinity is immanent, not transcendent. All beings are interdependent and interconnected and expressions of one substance. Arguably, Western philosophies, Judaeo-Christian and liberal humanists emphasizes on logic, dominion and stewardship while Eastern philosophies particularly Hinduism lays stress on harmony, pantheism and spiritualisation of ecology. The most revered principle: 'Jivo Jivasya Jivnam' in Indian philosophy. Every living being has an inherent right to live, evolve and seek its own well-being. In this research paper, literature-related methods are employed by examining primary scriptures and studying scholarly articles of western and eastern philosophers. To examine how both Eastern and Western philosophies to promote environmental studies. Welfare of all beings. Compassion and unconditional love for all amounts to an ecological virtue. This research study reveals that ancient Indian religious or spiritual traditions substantially enriched contemporary ecological consciousness. These philosophies have the immense relevance today to avert environmental crisis and to promote sustainable way of living.

Key words: Consciousness, Anthropocentrism, Eastern, Western, Ethics, God, Nature

Introduction:

Both Western and Eastern philosophies present metaphysical worldview as well as ecological concern. Arguably, Western philosophies, Judaeo-Christian and liberal humanists emphasizes on logic, dominion and stewardship while Eastern philosophies particularly Hinduism lays stress on harmony, pantheism and spiritualisation of ecology. Both philosophies taught the world sustainable environmental ethics must transcend anthropocentrism.

Pantheistic approach too helps us in understanding this issue in a better way. Universe and God are identical. In simple language, pantheism is the juxtaposition of man, nature and God. God is present everywhere. Omnipresent, omniscient and omnipotent. God is pervading in nature, in living beings and in the whole universe. It means divinity in all existence. There is no one separate personal God. In Romantic poetry, one can witness pantheistic vision of poets. The most prominent among them is William Wordsworth. He believes that nature is a living spirit. God's presence can be witnessed in flowers, mountains, rivers and forests. God is present in all elements of nature. Nature as sacred and humanity is spirituality connected with nature. Nature provides moral, spiritual and emotional guidance to all.

Universe is eternal. Human being dies, but the essence remains. This self- functioning inverse is aligned with basic concepts of pantheism. This divinity is within the universe itself, not outside it. Jainism traditionally believes in pantheistic vision as it shares similar ideas. Nature enlivens the human spirit. Self-realization liberates human soul. Even in Jainism too represent inner divine nature of the soul. For them, the divine is not something external, but it is inside the self- that is the key concept of pantheistic philosophy.

Objectives:

1. To analyse the key pantheistic elements, present in Hinduism in particular and Western environmental philosophies and explore their relevance in protecting the environment.
2. To analyse the concepts of Man, God and Nature and pantheism through an ecological perspective.
3. To examine how both Eastern and Western philosophies to promote environmental studies.

Hypothesis Statement:

The basic tenets of Hinduism and Western philosophies laid down a strong foundation for environmental ethics. They taught the world pantheistic philosophy, interconnectedness and independence of all forms of life. Close study of this religion reveals a strong inclination towards non-violent, responsible and sustainable way of living.

Research Methodology: Comparative content analysis is done to identify pantheistic and ecological themes in Western and Eastern philosophies. Literature-related methods are employed by examining primary scriptures and studying scholarly articles. Through the

ecological and philosophical lenses which highlight sacredness, interconnection and interactions between all human forms, are closely studied to reach to the conclusion.

Literature Review

Western Pantheistic Philosophy and Respect for Nature:

It is the popular belief that everything is the manifestation of all encompassing, immanent divine force. Universe and God are identical. In simple language, it is the juxtaposition of man, nature and God. God is present everywhere. Omnipresent, omniscient and omnipotent. God is pervading in nature, in living beings and in the whole universe. It means divinity in all existence. There is no one separate personal God. In Romantic poetry, one can witness pantheistic vision of poets. The most prominent among them is William Wordsworth. He believes that nature is a living spirit. God's presence can be witnessed in flowers, mountains, rivers and forests

One of the Western philosophers, Baruch Spinoza (1632-1677) is very much aligned with modern pantheism. Argumentatively, he laid the foundation for environmental ethics. His writings 'God or Nature' affirms that God is not separate from the universe. Everything that exists is an expression of one God. Divinity is immanent, not transcendent. All beings are interdependent and interconnected and expressions of one substance. Thus, such an ideology of Spinoza inculcates environmentally responsible behaviour. He refuted human-centred approach. He also denies the popular perception that humans are superior than all forms of life. In the great chain of being, the natural laws govern everything which argues for equal respect for all forms of life. Divinity is immanent, not transcendent. He equated nature with God. In the great chain of being, the natural laws govern everything which argues for equal respect for all forms of life. In addition to this Spinoza says that true freedom comes from understanding nature and living harmoniously with all forms of life. Interaction with nature improves mental health. Nature has such a healing power. Rationalistic western ideology believes that all needs to understand the limitations of the natural world. All needs to behave in such a way that sustains the nature and making rational long-term decisions to protect the environment. Thus, western pantheistic philosophy of Spinoza regarding God or Nature encourages environmental care not merely as a duty but a spiritual and philosophical necessity.

Discussion:

After reading this philosophy, or learns the truth that universe is not a bundle of isolated objects but a vast living expanse, a living unity. Essentially, one needs to understand that nature is not just an object of beauty, but she is holy and divine. Everything in the universe is interconnected and God exists in every part of it. William Wordsworth (1770-1850) is the staunch supporter of the pantheism. He feels deep spiritual connection with nature. For him, nature is nurse, teacher, friend and philosopher.

“Through primrose tufts, in that green bower,
The periwinkle trailed its wreaths;
And 'tis my faith that every flower
Enjoys the air it breathes.”

“Have I not reason to lament
What man has made of man? (Wordsworth, 1798)

There is an essential difference between pantheism and traditional religion. Instead of offering prayers in the temples, a true pantheist finds peace by sitting under a tree and listening to sweet piping of the piper. It also comforts with the belief human beings are not truly alone in this universe, God is always around us. Human beings are closer to God by loving and respecting the natural world. The poet here believes in spiritual vitality present in the nature. Wordsworth is fascinated by the wonders of nature. According to him, nature contains a "living soul". Wordsworth refers here 'Presence' that disturbs him positively, here sees presence of some invisible divine power. As a result, the landscape becomes animated with inner life. 'Disturbs with joy' this phrase indicates an encounter with the divine power which is not confined with religious sentiments. Such moments of insights are quite familiar to us in his poetry. He suggests that nature nourishes the mind and moulds one's moral consciousness. Through frequent visits to nature, one can attain a heightened sense peace, unity and ethical clarity. This is in alignment with pantheistic idea that God communicates with us through the rhythms of natural landscape. It is nothing but the splendid manifestation of deep contemplation of the nature.

Thus, Wordsworth's depiction of nature in "Tintern Abbey" transcends traditional Romantic appreciation of beauty. It evolves into a spiritual doctrine in which the boundaries between humanity, nature, and divinity dissolve. The poem stands as one of the most influential

literary expressions of Romantic pantheism, presenting nature as the visible form of an all-pervading spiritual reality. Such a depiction of natural landscape in the famous poem like "Tintern Abbey " transcends traditional belief system and it evolves into spiritual communion in which boundaries between nature, humanity and divinity totally dissolve. Above lines are the most powerful expressions of pantheism, presenting nature as the visible form of an all -pervading divinity. Divinity in all beings. Divine essence pervades everywhere. (George Bulher, 1886)

Humans, plants, animals even tiny insects, microorganisms, earth- bodies, fire - bodies air-bodies possess Jiva - means all forms of life -bodies possess Jiva (Soul). One must remember that nature is not for satisfying the hunger of man, but a web of living entities deserving understanding and compassion. Jainism detests harming even the smallest microorganism emphasizes limiting consumption. (Always eat less than what is required) and focuses on protecting biodiversity. Ethics learned from Jainism encourages minimalism, non-exploitation and vegetarianism which is in consonance with modern principles of environmental sustainability. Strictly, Jainism has non- theistic approach towards nature. The whole existence is self- regulated, self - controlled and is governed by the natural laws without any intervention from any deity. Liberation of an individual person can be achieved through self- efforts without divine intervention. Environmental ethics of Jainism strengthens the foundation of environmental studies. It primarily believes that nature is not created by some unknown material forces and humans have no authority to exploit it. Since human being is a moral agent of change whose behaviour affects all living and non-living things. They can do severe ecological damage through their careless behaviour or they are capable of showing highest ethical conduct through restraint, resilience and non-violence. For example, Jain five vows Ahimsa, Aparigrah, Satya, Asteya and Brahmacharya even though implicitly, shape ecological consciousness. The most revered principle: 'Jivo Jivasya Jivnam' in Indian philosophy. Every living being has an inherent right to live, evolve and seek its own well-being. It reflects the pantheistic philosophy, especially in terms of sacredness and interconnectedness of all existence. This principal 'Live and Let Live' aligns with the pantheistic idea that the world is the sacred place to live in and shows profound respect for every living being. It remains a cosmic vision of harmony where every life is revered and it constitutes ecological consciousness. The entire universe is treated with care, empathy and most importantly with responsibility

Sarva Bhūta Hita (सर्व भूत हित) — Welfare of all beings. Compassion and unconditional love for all amounts to an ecological virtue. It extends its moral principle of humanity for the welfare of all living beings. Its origin is found in Upanishadic ethics. The welfare of humanity ultimately on the welfare of all living beings.

Dhāraṇā or Dharti-Dharma — It is the duty of humanity to sustain it. Or the sole aim of any Dharma for that matter is sustainability. It encourages to look at environmental stewardship as a moral responsibility. This aligns with the concept of modern ecological activism and policy ethics. The Isha Upanishad's principle- "Isavasyam idam saryam" preaches that the entire universe is nothing but the manifestation of divinity. So much so that, even different aspects of nature are revered as deities, Ganga-purifying, Prithvi-Mother earth, Surya- Sun God, Agni, Vayu, Varuna as the divine elements. This outlook encourages reverence, conservation and protection of nature. Five elements (Panchmahabhutas) like Prithvi (earth), Jala (water), Tejas / Agni (fire), Vayu(air) and Akasha(space). These elements maintain delicate cosmic balance, however, there is a disruption brought out by human intervention - like air pollution, water- pollution, soil erosion etc and disturb this delicate balance and thus violation of dharma. What Hindu philosophy believes that everyone has not only a legal or social responsibility, but ethical and moral duties to protect the environment. (Radhakrishnan, 1994). This one can see as an individual dharma. These duties include: a. Daya-Compassion and unconditional love for all

b. Ahimsa- Avoiding harm c. Aparigraha- Controlling senses-restrain and resilient. d. Shouchya- Maintaining purity.

Isha Upanishada preaches that this natural universe too is governed by Divine force and should be used to satisfy our need and not greed. It should be used with restraint. In the Vedic literature, there is a cosmic law which keeps universe in order. But due to the human intervention, this order is being disturbed. It is creating natural imbalance. This is happening due to overuse of natural resources and unsustainable activities. Therefore, environmental protection has become not only a social or legal duty, but a moral and spiritual duty for maintain balance in natural cycles, cosmic harmony and ecological rhythms. (Bloomfield,1987). This dictum 'Isavasyam idam sarvam' teaches to take what is necessary and do not covet. This justifies the idea about protecting environment as a spiritual duty. It goes further and teaches that one should not cause injury to animals and plants and protecting this beautiful natural world is a part of one's daily duty.

मया ततमिदं सर्वं जगदव्यक्तमूर्तिना । मत्स्थानि सर्वभूतानि न चाहं तेष्ववस्थितः ॥ ४ ॥

This beautiful verse from Bhagavad Gita explains that God is the substratum of all the universe. The entire existence is pervaded by Him, but He remains transcendent (Unmanifest form). He is untouched by creation and destruction. The entire universe exists within him. This concept can be understood subjectively. One finds milk as an unadulterated substance. It can be transformed into yoghurt with acid. But the basic substratum that is milk remains the same in the same. Yoghurt is the product (effect) of milk. In the same way, God has produced this world and is situated everywhere. This means that God is not separate from nature and therefore destroying nature means harming the very presence of God. Pollution, animal cruelty, desertification, deforestation, commercialisation and overconsumption violate the very dharma of a person. If one understands this environmentally, one understands that protecting the environment means protecting the divinity in the universe.

It is a profound spiritual obligation in Hindu philosophy. Pantheism the very word is derived from the Greek words, "Pan" means "all" and "theos" means "God" Oxford Dictionary defines "Pantheism" as "The view that God is in everything, or that God and the universe are one". It is the popular belief that everything is the manifestation of all encompassing, immanent divine force. Universe and God are identical. In simple language, it is the juxtaposition of man, nature and God. God is present everywhere. Omnipresent, omniscient and omnipotent. God is pervading in nature, in living beings and in the whole universe. It means divinity in all existence. There is no one separate personal God. In Romantic poetry, one can witness pantheistic vision of poets. The most prominent among them is William Wordsworth. He believes that nature is a living spirit. God's presence can be witnessed in flowers, mountains, rivers and forests. God is present in all elements of nature. Nature as sacred and humanity is spirituality connected with nature. Nature provides moral, spiritual and emotional guidance to all. While Jainism preached that all living beings have Jiva, Soul. Every Jiva is inherently pure, divine and can get liberation from the vicious cycle of life and death. Actually, this respect for all forms is germinated from the concept of ahimsa.

Jainism does not believe in a creator God. Universe is eternal. Human being dies, but the essence remains. This self- functioning inverse is aligned with basic concepts of pantheism. This divinity is within the universe itself, not outside it. Jainism traditionally believes in pantheistic vision as it shares similar ideas. Nature enlivens the human spirit. Self-realization liberates human soul. Self- realised Tirthankars like Rishabhdeva, Mahavira represent inner divine nature of the soul. For them, the divine is not something external, but it is inside the self- that is the key concept of pantheistic philosophy.

The above discussion reveals that Hinduism accommodates pantheistic notion of the divinity. Jainism and its ethical implications support environmental protection. Both the philosophies of Jainism and Hinduism, there is a significant convergence if one needs to interpret the relationship between man, nature and God from the pantheistic point of view. Hinduism accommodates pantheistic notion of the divinity. Jainism and its ethical implications support environmental protection. Both philosophies show remarkable alignment. Both promote strong environmental ethics. Hinduism promotes the view the divine force permeates the entire universe and it is instrumental in encouraging ecological sensitivity, reverence for the natural world and most significantly interconnectedness between all beings. While Jainism emphasizes on Purity, Karma and non-injury. Protecting nature is a moral obligation, since every action has cosmic consequence. Human beings should minimise harm to the nature, even if unintentionally. Both the philosophies of Jainism and Hinduism, there is a significant convergence if one needs to interpret the relationship between man, nature and God from the pantheistic point of view.

One needs to understand the following perspectives.

1. Environment- as an object of dominion while Lovelock believes in ecological holism and Confucian in Eco- civilisation. Aquinas, Kant believe in anthropocentric stewardship. According to these philosophers, humanity and nature are the finest expressions of the same cosmic reality. There has to be balance between human activities and nature. Identification and empathy with all forms of life are the hallmarks of this ontological view. Buddhism believes that all things arise independently. (*Pratitya-samutpada*).
2. The illusion of separateness causes depression and consequently ecological balance. When one perceives the interdependence of all life, one naturally refrains from harm to sentient or insentient beings. Daoism believes that nature is the ultimate teacher. The well-known dictum of The Dao De says, “Human follows Earth, Earth follows Heaven, Heaven follows Dao, and Dao follows its own nature” Therefore, the best action is non-coercive or natural action. Ecological ethics is a spiritual realism and not a moral duty. Harmonious life sustain itself and the cosmos simultaneously.
3. Eco-humanism is the very comprehensive term which synthesises western and eastern views. It affirms harmony between human dignity and ecological interdependence. This is what is called as Integrative philosophy of the modern era. There is a paradigm

shift from human dominion to human coexistence. Arne Naess another philosopher of Deep Ecology views that humanity is not above but it resides within nature. “Humans are not above but within nature”. For Naess, “the higher self is the ecological self - realizing unity with all life”. Western philosophy teaches why we have to care, Eco-humanism how personally, socially and politically contribute to conserve humanism. While Eastern philosophy teaches what care, one needs to take to maintain and sustain the earth.

Conclusion:

Western philosophy teaches why we have to care, Eco-humanism how personally, socially and politically contribute to conserve humanism. While Eastern philosophy teaches what care, one should take to maintain and sustain the earth. Pantheism acts as a bridge between eco- consciousness and religiosity found in the eastern philosophy. These two philosophies develop deep respect and reverence for the natural world as sacred place filled with divinity. Conservation of nature is not just material need but also spiritual obligation. Such concept of environmentalism acts as a philosophical framework to encourage environmental ethics like treating nature as a sacred-beings, establish strong bonding between the environment and human beings and thereby inculcating the harmonious way of living.

This research study reveals that ancient Indian religious or spiritual traditions substantially enriched contemporary ecological consciousness. These philosophies have the immense relevance today to avert environmental crisis and to promote sustainable way of living. Divine immanence of Hinduism and non-violent ethics of Jainism both philosophies place environmental protection at the centre of our moral responsibility. These philosophies have the immense relevance today to avert environmental crisis and to promote sustainable way of living.

Scope for further Study: To create awareness, deeper philosophical exploration can be undertaken to find out all pervading divinity. The interaction and interdisciplinary approaches between environmental studies, religious study and even sociology can assimilate and construct more holistic framework for spiritual ecology in this modern world.

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